

PSYCHOLOGICAL SCIENCES

EARLY CARE FOR CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS AND THEIR FAMILIES: THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL ANALYSIS

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Abstract

The article cited the problem of autism and scientific trends in early care. At the same time, the article provides scientific coverage of such concepts as social deficiency in a person, the formation of a physical defect in a person as a complex derivative of psychological, medical, social, economic and spiritual factors, in which children with autism syndrome belong to a person with special needs, modern interpretations of the definition of "early help" were covered. The benefits of "early care" not only for children, but also for families, were scientifically substantiated. The article scientifically analyzed the opinions and conclusions of scientists, specialists of research institutes on this problem.

Keywords: early care, autism, family, integrated care, systematic approach, defective child, social communication, development line.

Methods

Methodology

Autism is one of the severe types of mental disorder, which is manifested by trying to withdraw from others and not being able to express emotions in the way we are used to. Autism is caused by neurological disorders that directly affect the functioning of the brain. In most cases, autism appears in children under the age of 3, but most parents do not pay attention to its first signs. The signs of autistic disorder are more likely to appear at the age of 2-3 years. In the early stages of autism, the child does not respond to certain actions of the parents, and reacts to them with indifference. He cannot establish friendly and warm relations with the surrounding people, relatives, and their children. They do not respond to their parents' sweet words and caresses with a smile, they have the same attitude towards inanimate objects and people. Another key symptom is the inability to look others in the eye. They try not to catch the eyes of the people around them. Speech disorders, inability to speak, inability to play games that require a creative approach can also be signs of autism. Studies have shown that children with autism have homogeneity in their actions, sleep disorders, aggressiveness, and fear. What exactly causes autism in children has not been fully studied by scientists. Unlike Down, Patau, Marfan and other types of syndromes, no genetic anomalies are noted in the patient's body in autism. Experts say that in most children with autism, this condition is caused by difficulties during the birth process and pregnancy. When disturbances in brain activity begin to be observed, hyperactivity and a decrease in intelligence are noted in the patient. However, experts say that it is difficult to diagnose autism based on certain symptoms.

Participants

A doctor's help and a number of tests are needed to make an accurate diagnosis. The earlier the diagnosis, the sooner parents and professionals can start the treatment process. Some children with autism graduate from high school, learn a profession, and work in pres-

tigious places. Nevertheless, it is very difficult for people with autism to trace their personal life and start a family. Experts suggest several methods for treating autism. According to them, it is necessary to provide all kinds of help to a young patient. During the treatment of the syndrome, great attention is paid to improving the child's relationship with parents and other family members, he is taught to overcome fear and fight against aggressive attacks. A lot of responsibility is required from parents of children with autism. The most important thing is not to take autism as a terrible sentence. Asperger's syndrome is a type of autism, in which the mental potential is preserved, the patient speaks with others, but cognitive functions work well, the symptoms of mental retardation are not visible, but it is difficult for them to adapt to the people around them. Children with Asperger's syndrome try to distance themselves from people, and they may not understand what they are saying. At the same time, his intellectual potential will not be inferior to that of children of the same age, and he may even surpass them in intellectual directions. Children with Asperger's syndrome are distinguished by their interest in a certain direction. For example, they can watch one show on TV endlessly, play only one of hundreds of toys endlessly. It has its own positive side, actually. A child with Asperger's syndrome is attentive to the activity he is interested in, and shows interest even in small details. Most of them achieve excellent results in mathematics, music, drawing.

Data Collection

Explaining the main features of the development of the human psyche with biological laws - heredity - is a mistake from a theoretical point of view. It causes great difficulties in practice. Because here the role of the educator is reduced. Age and pedagogic-psychology are based on the idea that the laws of human mental development are determined by the complex set of social conditions of child upbringing and life. This raises the question of what is the role of neurophysiological characteristics in the development of the biological conditions of development. Human mental activity is

very complex. Its characteristics depend on the upbringing and life of the child. Logical memory, abstract thinking, perception of objects, etc., higher mental functions are not transmitted or strengthened by hereditary biological means. This allows to reconstruct and improve them in the process of historical development. In modern science, a fairly large number of interpretations of the definition of "early help" have been formed. Depending on scientific trends, ideas, and time periods, researchers distinguish different points of view. "Initially, early care was considered as a complex of services for medical, social, psychological and pedagogical services for infants and young children. Then this concept was supplemented, and later it was defined as a set of social network services that support families with young children and directly and/or indirectly affect the functioning of a family with a child as a whole. "By the mid-90s of the twentieth century, early care was considered as a model of psychological and social assistance, when the prevention of problems in the development of a child was considered more important than the correction of existing disorders. The end of the last century and the beginning of this century have confirmed the idea of early care as an integral part of a family-centered approach in the implementation of psychosocial care. Based on this approach, Western researchers formulate their definition of early care: "Early care can best be defined as a system created to support family patterns of interaction that most contribute to the development of the child"[1].

Ethical Considerations

According to a number of Russian researchers, "early care is a set of measures aimed at promoting optimal development, improving the health and well-being of infants, early and preschool children with disabilities and the risk of such restrictions, normalizing family life, increasing the competence of parents (legal representatives), including the child in the environment of peers and community life" [2, pp.4-5].

Researchers of the St. Petersburg Institute of Early Intervention have included in the concept of "early care" not only assistance to children, but also to their families. "Early assistance to children and their families is a complex of early assistance services provided on an interdisciplinary and interdepartmental basis to children of the target group and their families, aimed at promoting the physical and mental development of children, their involvement in natural life situations, the formation of positive interaction and relationships between children and parents/caregivers in the family as a whole, promoting the inclusion of children in the environment of peers and their integration into society"[3, p. 4-18].

Analytic Strategy

Early care for children with special needs pursues a number of goals inherent in the whole world:

- early detection of any abnormalities in the development of the child, as well as early prevention of the consequences of deviations;
- "formation and development of the ability of young children with disabilities or the risk of their occurrence to independent life in society;

- reducing the costs of special education for children and thus reducing the need for special education and care after they reach school age;

- providing assistance to parents in creating optimal conditions for the development and education of a child in a family and local community;

- increasing the level of competence of parents and other family members, leading to the expansion and strengthening of their capabilities to meet the special needs of their child;

- promotion of social integration of family and child"[4, p. 8].

This type of assistance is also provided to children with autism, under the age of three, with risk factors in development. Children with ASD and families raising children with such a diagnosis can receive the necessary support in educational, health, social protection institutions and is organized in accordance with the procedure established by law. "Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are a group of disorders characterized by qualitative deviations in social interactions and sociability indicators, as well as a limited, stereotypical, repetitive set of interests and actions" [5]. Currently, many researchers use the generalized name of authentic conditions of children as "autism spectrum disorders". This is due to the fact that each category of disorders included in this spectrum has many different features, but all of them, one way or another, are derivatives of the same disorder. The starting point for substantiating the approach that allows us to understand and evaluate the true essence of a complex, multidimensional and multifaceted phenomenon, such as early care, was the idea of it as an integral social system. A system is a complex of objects, as well as the relationship between objects and their attributes (definitions). Objects are components of a system, attributes are properties of parts, and relationships bind the system together. The systematic approach creates conditions for the consistent solution of research tasks by considering the phenomenon of early care through the prism of its role, place, value-target orientations and functions in a more complex system of different countries – the social system, due to a holistic, integrative and targeted vision of the object and the management system, their connections and development [6]. Starting from 60-70.

Analysis

In the twentieth century, projects, programs, and various initiatives in support of early assistance to children with developmental disabilities and their families developed rapidly in the United States, so this country can rightfully be considered the birthplace of the definition and development of early assistance to children with autism spectrum disorders and their families. During this period, a new understanding of human rights and the rights of persons with disabilities begins to form in American society against the background of economic recovery and the beginning of the transition from an industrial to a post-industrial society. The approaches, concepts, and scientific ideas described in various psychological directions about the development of the infant served as the foundation for the formation and development of the early care system.

Thus, S. Freud, a representative of the classical psychoanalytic school, believed that "social ties and relationships between mother and child are interpreted as a transformation of libidinal tendencies"[1]. In his opinion, a child is initially born with a sexual attraction, the so-called "libido". Since parents are the first people who attract the child's attention, they become the first objects of libido. Starting from the age of 3-5 years, a child experiences attachment to a parent of the opposite sex, such attachment is S. Freud defined both the Oedipus complex in boys and the Electra complex in girls. The resolution of these complexes leads to the identification of a child with a parent of the same sex and the internalization of parental prohibitions, moral norms and models of gender-role behavior. After the end of the Second World War, when most children were separated from their mothers and other family members, psychoanalysts raise the problem of the infant's connection with the mother. In this context, S. Freud developed the concept of the line of development. The main idea of the concept is that the child is helpless from birth, completely attached to the mother, then from the moment of growing up gradually becomes emotionally self-sufficient and independent. S. Freud's ideas and his daughters formed the basis of Margaret Mahler's theory of child individualization. Within the framework of this theory, children go through 3 stages of formation as a person. The very first stage, which according to the theory is called autistic, the child passes from birth (the 1st month of life), he is characterized as a biological being. The child's behavior is primitive and non-integrated. At the second stage (symbiotic, 2-5 months), the child merges with the mother. The third stage is the individualization of the child, i.e. the separation of the child from the mother. Psychologist John Bowlby, within the framework of his theory of attachment, proved the connection between the relationship of mother and child for the further development of the latter. The central idea of attachment theory is that the immediate environment, which initially takes care of the baby, responds to his needs and satisfies them, allows the child to feel safe. The infant knows that this or that adult is reliable, and this gives him support for further knowledge of the world. The researcher argued that there is some kind of connection between the mother and the baby, the rupture of this connection leads to a violation in mental development, as well as in the structure of the child's personality. John Bowlby argued that children who have had proper maternal care show a higher level of self-confidence and ability to adapt to environmental conditions. The following approaches that have influenced the development of early care are behavioral and non-behavioral approaches. The first approach is characterized by the concept of "learning". The infant acts "as a natural being, adapting by learning to the conditions of individual life on the basis of the presence or absence of reinforcement." The second approach is characterized by the concepts of "social learning", "social reactivity" and "social reinforcement". The main advantage of this approach is "the clarity of the experimental formulation of the problem and the accumulation of a large amount of factual material characterizing the child's capabilities and their expansion

during the first year of life, considering the child in interaction with an adult"[1]. The concept of the German psychologist D. Stern supplemented the knowledge about early development. The main idea of his concept was that first children develop perception, then memory and only then thinking. "The provisions of the concept served as the basis for the creation of a psychotherapeutic approach focused on the mother–infant system. The spheres of healthcare, social protection, as well as special education in the USA at the turn of the 60s had a significant impact on the formation of the system of early care for children and their families. Children from the earliest age, as well as their families, receive assistance directly in health care institutions. This assistance includes consultations and receptions of doctors of various profiles: pediatricians, neurologists, psychiatrists, ophthalmologists, physiotherapists, speech therapists and other specialists. M. Seligman and R.B. Darling in their book "Ordinary families, special children" (2007), said that during the 60s of the XX medical care it was focused mainly only on a sick child who was a patient of the health service. With this approach, only specialists decided what was best for the child, and the family was provided with the necessary information about the course of the diagnostic process or treatment of the child, and such treatment was carried out within the walls of medical institutions. Thus, the family practically did not participate in the recovery of their children. During the course of medical procedures, the family was given recommendations on daily child care, but despite this, they were mostly of a general nature. With this approach, the family was obliged to follow the recommendations of specialists. The negative perception of children with special needs, as well as the relationship between specialists and parents, prompted specialists to consider the child's family members as a "second patient". The parents were assigned the "role of the patient" – to be ready for cooperation, to agree with all the opinions and decisions of professionals. According to researchers M. Seligman and R.B. Darling, the 60s of the last century combined a clinical approach with an emphasis on "placing blame on the victim" and a professionally dominant approach in order to suppress the resistance of parents of children with special needs. But soon such a position of the association undermined the trust and respect for the specialists of medical institutions. Since 1950, studies have been conducted to assess the public's trust in healthcare professionals. It turned out that since the 1950s, the level of public confidence in medical personnel began to decline, and by 1975, only 43% of the population treated medical personnel with respect and trust [6]. Considering many factors that served as prerequisites for the creation of an early care system in the United States, a number of researchers identified the first experiments on family-oriented care organized in the healthcare system. These are the Cornell project (1939-1941) and the Montefiore Medical Group project (1950-1959) [1]. In 1939, the Cornell Project was launched in New York. The meaning of it was to identify the relationship between health and climate in the family. 15 families were involved in the project, and it took two years to collect and analyze

the data. Due to the outbreak of World War II, the project was interrupted. After the end of the war, the Montefiore Medical Group project (1950-1959) was launched. The main purpose of which was to determine the possibility of preventing the disease in a family member by working with the whole family as a whole. The project involved 100 families and a large group of specialists of various profiles. However, analyzing the data of the Montefiore Medical Group project, researchers M. Seligman and R.B. Darling, noted that the potential of the project was not fully realized, and this was due to specialists who did not want to expand their professional activities by taking on new roles that were not characteristic of their profession. The reason for the development of early assistance programs for children with special needs was the programs implemented in the 60s and 70s for children from low-income families. Programs were developed for teaching children with developmental disabilities, approximately up to the age of third grade, and were implemented by both non-profit and state institutions. This is how the system of early assistance to children with special needs began to emerge. The early assistance program included a wide variety of problems: "problems of early education of children; problems of support and support of family members of a special child; stimulating the development of infants and the education of their mothers; family rehabilitation programs; programs for the care of children and adolescents, etc. [1, p.25]. At the very beginning, early care was provided point-by-point and was not organized in all states of America, it was mainly supported by parent associations, groups and associations. Then, with the achievement of good results of early assistance to children with disabilities and their families, early assistance programs began to spread throughout the country, which laid down a mechanism for interaction between various departments at the state level or interaction between non-governmental non-profit organizations and government agencies [1, p.25]. In society during this period, there is a rethinking of the attitude towards children with special needs. "The main value orientations of the new philosophy began to cover the following areas of the life of the child and his family: the creation of normal living conditions for the child in the family; the creation of conditions for the development of the child together with the family: the presence of developing communication, play environment, special and developmental activities, information, education and training of family members in order to provide the maximum possible assistance to the child; creation of a normal social environment surrounding the child in the family and outside it, when visiting a kindergarten, a developmental center, a clinic, etc." [1, pp.25-26]. With the development of the system of early assistance to children with special needs, there is a special literature describing various technologies of assistance, methodological approaches, giving recommendations to specialists, as well as parents raising special children. The most popular were the management of "Portage" and the management of "Carolina". The programs are aimed at supporting young children (from birth to 2 years old) with developmental disabilities. Programs solve the problem of developing

a special child in two ways. "Firstly, the skills in each area of development are divided into logical sections of training. Secondly, the content of many sections included changes for children with sensory and motor limitations"[1, p. 26]. Russian researcher N.S. Groznaya, coordinator of editorial and publishing activities of Downside Up, in her article identified three stages in the formation of early care for children with disabilities. The first period of the history of the development of early care falls on the late 1950s - early 1960s. This period is associated with the period of development of programs for low-income families. The first program was "Head Start", which in translation meant "a starting leap", aimed at combating poverty. During this period, large monetary investments are noted for the development of various social programs. However, due to the lack of a reliable regulatory and theoretical framework, waste and investments were inevitable. The same thing happened in the second period (late 1960s- early 1970s). The third period in the history of early aid formation (1970s-1980s) was financially limited, but despite this, huge strides were made in the development of early aid. The implemented social programs during this period were based on studies of the development of young children. Since the 70s, a large amount of specialized literature on early intervention and assistance to children with special needs and their families has been published [7, pp. 3-8]. At the present stage in Russia, the system of early care is at the stage of formation. "The formation of a system of early diagnosis of developmental abnormalities and early comprehensive care occurs through the development of a system of medical, psychological and pedagogical patronage, which is carried out on the basis of existing psychological, medical and pedagogical centers and psychological, medical and pedagogical consultations and services"[8]. A number of scientists, such as V. M. Bekhtereva, N. M. Shchelovanova, N. I. Kasatkina, N. M. Askarina, laid the foundation for the formation of early aid in our country. In their works, the researchers described the factors that influence the formation of a child's personality at an early age. They emphasized the importance of an adult on the formation of a child's personality, their relationship [9]. Thus, summing up the first paragraph, we can say that the concept of "early help" has different interpretations. This term can be viewed from various points of view: as an ideology and model of psychosocial care; as a social program with its own strategic plan; as a system of technologies; as a complex of diagnostic and correctional processes; as a set of measures for rehabilitation, habilitation of an interdisciplinary team of specialists; as a social policy. "Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) is a group of disorders characterized by qualitative deviations in social interactions and indicators of sociability, as well as a limited, stereotypical, repetitive set of interests and activities" [10]. Currently, many researchers use the generalized name of the authentic conditions of children as "autism spectrum disorders". This is due to the fact that each category of disorders included in this spectrum has many different features, but all of them, one way or another, are derivatives of the same disorder.

The starting point for substantiating the approach that allows understanding and evaluating the true essence of a complex, multidimensional and multifaceted phenomenon, which is early assistance, was the idea of it as an integral social system. A system is a complex of objects, as well as relationships between objects and their attributes (definitions). Objects are the constituent parts of the system, attributes are the properties of the parts, and relationships bind the system together.

The systematic approach creates conditions for the consistent solution of research problems by considering the phenomenon of early assistance through the prism of its role, place, value-target orientations and functions in a more complex system of various countries - the social system, due to a holistic, integrative and targeted vision of the object and the control system, their connections and development [11].

Starting from the 60-70s. In the 20th century, projects, programs, and various initiatives to support early intervention for children with developmental disabilities and their families were rapidly developing in the United States, so this country can rightly be considered the birthplace of the definition and development of early intervention for children with autism spectrum disorders and their families. During this period, in American society, against the backdrop of economic recovery and the beginning transition from an industrial to a post-industrial society, a new understanding of human rights and the rights of persons with disabilities is beginning to form. Approaches, concepts, scientific ideas about the development of an infant described in various psychological directions served as the foundation for the formation and development of the early assistance system.

Thus, Z. Freud, a representative of the classical psychoanalytic school, believed that "social ties and relationships between mother and child are interpreted as a transformation of libidinal tendencies" [12]. In his opinion, a child is initially born with a sexual desire, the so-called "libido".

Since the parents are the first people to attract the child's attention, they become the first objects of the libido. Starting from the age of 3-5 years, the child experiences attachment to the parent of the opposite sex, such attachment Z. Freud defined as the Oedipus complex in boys and the Electra complex in girls. The resolution of these complexes leads to the identification of the child with a parent of the same sex and the internalization of parental prohibitions, moral norms and models of gender-role behavior. After the end of the Second World War, when most children were separated from their mothers and other family members, psychoanalysts raise the problem of the infant's connection with the mother.

In this context, A. Freud developed the concept of the line of development. The main idea of the concept is that a child is helpless from birth, completely attached to his mother, then from the moment of growing up he gradually becomes emotionally self-sufficient and independent.

The ideas of Z. Freud and his daughter formed the basis of Margaret Mahler's theory of individualization

of the child. Within the framework of this theory, children go through 3 stages of formation as a person. The very first stage, which according to the theory is called autistic, the child goes through from birth (1st month of life), he is characterized as a biological being.

The child's behavior is conspicuous and unintegrated. At the second stage (symbiotic, 2-5 months) merges the child with the mother. The third stage is the individualization of the child, i.e. separation of the child from the mother.

Psychologist John Bowlby, as part of his theory of attachment, proved the connection between the relationship between mother and child for the further development of the latter. The central idea of attachment theory is that the immediate environment, which initially cares for the baby, responds to his The baby knows that this or that adult is reliable, and this gives him support for the subsequent knowledge of the world. The researcher argued that there is some kind of connection between the mother and the baby, the rupture of this connection leads to a violation in mental development, as well as in the structure of the child's personality. John Bowlby argued that children who were properly maternally cared for showed higher levels of self-confidence and adaptability to environmental conditions needs and satisfies them, allows the child to feel safe. The next approaches that influenced the development of early intervention are the behavioral and non-behavioral approaches. The first approach is characterized by the concept of "learning". The infant acts "as a natural being, adapting by learning to the conditions of individual life on the basis of the presence or absence of reinforcement." The second approach is characterized by the concepts of "social learning", "social reactivity" and "social reinforcement".

The main advantage of this approach is "the clarity of the experimental formulation of the problem and the accumulation of a large amount of factual material characterizing the child's capabilities and their expansion during the first year of life, the consideration of the child in interaction with an adult"[12].

The concept of the German psychologist D. Stern supplemented the knowledge of early development. The main idea of his concept was that children first develop perception, then memory, and only then thinking. "Regulations concepts served as the basis for the creation of a psychotherapeutic approach focused on the mother-infant system. Significant influence on the formation of the system of early assistance to children and their families was provided by the spheres of health care, social protection, as well as special education in the United States at the turn of the 60s. Children from a very early age, as well as their families, receive assistance directly from health facilities. This assistance includes consultations and appointments with doctors of various profiles: pediatricians, neurologists, psychiatrists, ophthalmologists, physiotherapists, speech therapists and other specialists. M. Seligman and R.B. Darling in his book "Ordinary Families, Special Children" (2007), said that in the period of the 60s. XX medical care was focused mainly only on a sick child who was a patient of the health service.

Discussion

With this approach, only specialists decided what was best for the child, and the family was provided with the necessary information about the progress of the diagnostic process or treatment of the child, and such treatment was carried out within the walls of medical institutions. Thus, the family practically did not participate in the recovery of their children. In the process of carrying out medical procedures, the family was given recommendations on the daily care of the child, but despite this, they were mostly of a general nature. With this approach, the family was obliged to follow the recommendations of specialists. The negative image of children with special needs, as well as the relationship between specialists and parents, has led specialists to consider members of the child's family as a "second patient". Parents were entrusted with the "role of the patient" - to be ready for cooperation, to agree with all the opinions and decisions of professionals. According to researchers M. Seligman and R.B. Darling, 60s of the last century, a clinical approach with an emphasis on "putting the blame on the victim" and a professionally dominant approach have been combined in order to suppress the resistance of parents of children with special needs.

But soon this position of the association undermined the trust and respect for the specialists of medical institutions. Since 1950, studies have been carried out to assess the trust of the population in health care professionals. It turned out that since the 1950s, the level of public confidence in medical personnel began to decline, and by 1975, only 43% of the population treated medical personnel with respect and trust. Considering the many factors that led to the creation of the early intervention system in the United States, a number of researchers have identified the first experiments in family-oriented care organized in the health care system. These are the Cornell project (1939–1941) and the Montefiore medical group project (1950–1959) [12].

Summarizing the information from modern sources, the clinical and psychological symptoms characteristic of children's autism syndrome can be given as follows:

- communication disorder;
- disruption of social and emotional relationships;
- imagination disorder;
- behavior disorder;
- speech disorder;
- disturbance of cognitive processes.

Each of these signs is manifested in children in its own way. For example, communication disorder in an autistic child can be determined by his/her unwillingness or inability to communicate with others, lack of attention to the interlocutor during communication, lack of open expression of feelings, or lack of interest in expressed feelings. You can get more detailed information about the origin and symptoms of this syndrome through modern scientific and educational literature created by researchers and specialists of our country.

Children's autism is one of the unique problems of special pedagogy. The reason is that the above-mentioned features have a negative impact on the mental

and physical development of children, and hinder their socialization and integration processes.

In modern special pedagogy, there are many studies on correctional work with children with autism syndrome. In the following years, it is possible to observe a significant revival of this process in the CIS countries, in particular in Russia. At the same time, it cannot be denied that there is a need for scientific and practical research in Uzbekistan related to this syndrome in the medical, psychological and correctional-pedagogical fields in accordance with modern requirements.

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Usually, 3 areas of autism are clearly and clearly manifested:

- speech and communication;
- entering into social relations;
- imagination, emotion.

Difficulties with communication and socialization, lack of ability to establish emotional connections, disorders in speech development are explained as the main symptoms of autism, but it is also worth noting that autism affects every area of the psyche - mental and emotional, or Anomalous development of areas such as perception, motor skills, attention, memory, and speech is characteristic.

Despite the generality of disorders in the mental sphere, autism manifests itself in different forms. The book "Autistic child: ways to help" by O.S. Nikolskaya, Ye.R. Bayenskaya, and M.M. Lieblings gives examples of different approaches to distinguishing autistic children. According to him, the English researcher Dr. L. Wing divided such children into types such as "lonely" (does not seek to communicate), "passive" and "active, but clumsy" according to their ability to engage in social relations. lib explains. According to him, the group with a high probability of achieving social adaptation is the category of "passive" children. They propose to accept as a basis the classification according to the methods of being able to enter into communication and protection from it. They distinguish the main 4 forms of autism:

1. Complete indifference to the happening events, detachment from existence. Children with this form of autism show many deficiencies in their development and disturbances in their activity during early childhood. Later, they completely refuse to actively communicate with the outside world. Such children do not respond to the calls or appeals of others, they do not ask for anything, they do not develop goal-oriented behavior. They do not use speech and gestures and symbols. This is a severe form of autism, manifested in the child's complete detachment and indifference from the events around him.

2. Active rejection. Children of this group are relatively more active and less reluctant to communicate

with others, but they do not accept a large part of the world. For such children, it is very important to follow established life habits and established behaviors in a serious manner. They need to be surrounded by a familiar environment all the time, so their problems get worse as they get older - when it is necessary to get out of the inner environment of the house to a different external environment, to adapt, to communicate with new people. They have different movement habits. They can use speech, but their speech development is unique: first of all, they learn certain common words strictly associated with a specific situation. They seem to have a telegraphic style.

3. Preoccupation with autistic interests (or obsession). Children of this group are distinguished by their tendency to create conflict situations, not knowing how to take into account the interests and interests of others, and "immersing themselves" in the same activities and interests. These children are very "smart" and have a large vocabulary. However, they speak with very complex, "bookish" expressions, even their speech resembles the dull speech of adults. Despite their intellectual abilities, their ability to think is impaired, they cannot feel the essence and fundamental meaning of the situation, they have difficulty understanding the contents of several events that are happening at the same time.

4. Communicate and interact with too many difficulties. Lack of opportunities to establish relationships with other people is one of the central problems for children in this group. These children are characterized by difficulties in acquiring motor skills, their vocabulary is limited, their sentences are grammatically incorrect, they "lose themselves" in normal social situations. can "eat". This is one of the milder forms of autism.

According to statistics, autism in a deep form can be found in only one child out of a thousand. In everyday life, in preschool or school, we usually only come across children with some specific autistic symptoms. Autism is 4-5 times more common in boys than in girls.

Conclusions

The constructed model of organizing early care for children with autism and their families shows interdepartmental interaction between organizations (health, social protection, preschool education, non-profit organizations). All work of organizations in the field of early intervention should be based on the following basic principles:

- geographic and financial accessibility. Services should be accessible to the public and respond to the needs of the family raising a child with autism. The ability to easily and quickly get to social services, this is especially true for families living in rural areas;

- interdisciplinary work. The work of specialists in various fields providing early intervention services should be accompanied by a constant exchange of information and be based on partnerships;

- variety of programs and services. Comprehensive development of young children with autism spectrum disorders;

- relationship between professionals and families in providing early assistance to children with autism.

The model for optimizing the organization of early intervention for children with autism spectrum disorders and their families has two levels of delimitation of powers: regional and organizational level.

The first level (regional) includes the interaction of various departments: the Ministry of Health, the Ministry of Education and Science, the Ministry of Labor and Social Protection, and the Ministry of Economic Development.

This level is managing and coordinating, which implements the principles of public administration and performs the following functions:

- 1) management and coordination of activities of subjects of early intervention at the regional level;

- 2) organizational, informational, personnel, software and methodological support for the functioning of early aid,

- 3) regulatory and legal regulation of the activities of subjects of early intervention;

- 4) monitoring the effectiveness of early intervention for children with autism and their families. At the second level (level of organizations) carries out activities for providing timely entry of a family with a child with ASD into the system of early care, providing qualified medical, rehabilitation, habilitation assistance, as well as to determine the best ways to further preschool education or receive services in the field of additional education. Activities are carried out by the following organizations:

- 1) Organizations of the healthcare system (children's polyclinics, hospitals, maternity hospitals and other medical centers) are a key element in organizing early care for children with ASD. As soon as a diagnosis is made in a child, parents are immediately provided with information about the diagnosis, information is provided, i.e. addresses and telephone numbers of organizations involved in early intervention, so that parents do not waste time, but get involved in early intervention as soon as possible. Functions of organizations: early identification of needy families; complex diagnostics; treatment of existing disorders and prevention of secondary disorders; Information support.

- 2) Organizations of the social protection system and non-profit public organizations (rehabilitation centers for children, comprehensive centers for social services for the population, non-profit public organizations, foundations for supporting children with special needs, parent associations). The key task of these organizations is to create optimal conditions for the mental and social development of a child with autism spectrum disorders, to stimulate his potential in the process of special correctional and developmental influence and interaction of the child with parents and the outside world. Parents, especially those living in rural areas, should be given the opportunity to receive an on-line consultation from a psychologist. The main goal of Internet coaching is to help parents form a positive parenting attitude, which consists in unconditional acceptance of a child. The final stage of early assistance should be the transition to preschool educational institutions. Functions of organizations: social. rehabilitation; legal support; material support; parent coaching,

incl. through Internet technologies, information support.

3) Organizations of the education system (kindergartens, private educational centers). The early intervention program should end with the transfer and admission of the child to kindergarten. Functions of organizations: pre-school education: inclusive or special; additional education.

Early Assistance” - a set of medical, social, psychological and pedagogical services provided on an interdepartmental basis to children of the target group and their families, aimed at early identification of children of the target group, promoting their optimal development; Early Assistance is a family-centered program that aims to help not only the individual child, but also support the entire family.

The formation and development of the early intervention system for children with autism spectrum disorders was influenced by psychological concepts, scientific ideas about the development of the infant: the theory of individualization of the child (M. Mahler), attachment theory (J. Bowlby), behavioral and non-behavioral approaches.

The organization of early intervention in our country is based on family-centered work, including an interdisciplinary team of specialists operating on the basis of the healthcare system, education, social protection, and non-profit organizations. Since 1999, networks of early intervention services have been established on the basis of regional experiments.

They are represented in Samara and Novgorod, Nizhny Novgorod, Novosibirsk, Krasnoyarsk, Omsk regions, in St. Petersburg, Moscow. On the initiative of individual specialists, more than 400 different early intervention services for children operate in the Russian Federation.

As found in empirical research, the main steps in early intervention for children with autism spectrum disorders and their families are:

1) diagnostics 2) rehabilitation and habilitation

3) counseling parents about the characteristics of the child's development.

During the analysis of semi-structured interviews with specialists and parents, the advantages and disadvantages of organizing early assistance for children with autism spectrum disorders and their families were highlighted.

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